

TURKEY-EUROPEAN UNION RELATIONS FROM A SECURITY PERSPECTIVE

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This study examines the European Union-Turkey relations in the context of EU security policies and offers an analysis of the future of it. Turkey's post-Cold War era will be policy-oriented analysis on emerging new developments in the European security system. Moving work from this point ESDP (later the Common Security and Defense Policy) and the interests behind Turkey's role in ESDP/CSDP and aims to evaluate the contribution. This study focuses on Turkey's place in the European security and defense structures and the role of the EU's new regulation on the European security and defense architecture.

Introduction

The main purpose of the establishment of the European Union (EU) after the Second World War was to prevent future wars in the European Continent by controlling raw materials such as steel and coal through an organization. With this beginning, this organization, later known as the European Union (EU), turned into an economic and political cooperation between Western European countries and a free trade zone, customs union, common market and Common Security and Defense Policy (CSDP) were built in Europe. These founders who came up with the idea of the EU were of the opinion that the sovereignty of European states must be shared with a supranational European community in order to create a true security community. After the cold war, new international and regional political, economic, security and social security risks to Europe emerged. In the post-Cold War period, the European Union, which wanted to be a political power commensurate with its economic power in the international arena, realized that as a result of changing security parameters and threat perceptions, security and stability in the continent could not be fully achieved without a security structuring.

Developments in Europe after the Cold War forced the EU to establish common foreign and security policies and to work in harmony. The EU wants a separate security structure from NATO, which is the roof of European security. It strives for a Common Security Defense Policy (CSDP) and for a separate European Army. In this context, the EU revised its structure with the Maastricht, Amsterdam, Nice and Lisbon Treaties in order to protect from political, economic and security risks and to ensure prosperity and stability in Europe and its surroundings. It also wanted to improve CSDP / NATO cooperation to ensure European security. For this purpose, the EU firstly accepted the Central and Eastern European countries as members and expanded towards these regions. Afterwards, it tries to support the democratization processes in the countries of the region and integrate them into the economic and political structure of the EU. In addition, since the issue is directly related to the national sovereignty area, the area with the least cooperation in the EU is the field of security and defense policy. It is stated that the EU and the countries of the region are under a more complex and multidimensional threat compared to previous years. Increasing tension over nuclear weapons, terrorist attacks in European capitals, Russian expansionist politics, Arab Spring and instability in the Middle East, the civil war in Syria, Iraq and Libya, and in the Caucasus, North Africa and the Middle East terrorist

movements increasingly threaten Europe's stability and security. These developments have increased the security dependency between Europe's centre and its periphery. European security and stability has become more closely related to neighbouring regions (Mason 2018). These recent events have changed the threat perception and security interests not only for the EU but for the whole world.

For these reasons, the EU has become more interested in security issues (Onis, 2001; Duke, 2018; Mason 2018). In line with these developments, in order to become a more capable, coherent and strategic global actor, the EU revised its title targets for Europe's security capacity. In the new European security structuring that is taking shape, its impact on trans-Atlantic relations has been significant. While the USA expected a strong contribution from Europe on security issues, it did not want it to be a rival. In this context, the US generally pays attention to the compatibility of the European security and defense structure with NATO. New security structure that tries to shape the EU is also closely related to Turkey and Turkey-EU relations. NATO member Turkey as a regional player, is an important place in the European security. The establishment of close relations between the EU and Turkey to European security will contribute to contribute to the welfare and security of the EU and the environment.

Turkey's Role in European Security

Turkey has excluded the European security structure in the formation process of the European Security and Defense Policy. He was concerned about the exclusion of non-EU NATO members from the decision-making process of European security policies with the abolition of the BAB in 2000. Turkey has emphasized the necessity of direct participation in the process of taking decisions related to European security. Turkey wanted the rights it had acquired within the Western European Union to be protected. On the other hand, due to NATO membership, it reacted by keeping the veto right on the agenda for the operations to be organized by the EU with NATO facilities. According to Turkey this policy should be determined within the framework of a European security and defense together. Especially after the Summit process St.Malo developments in the European defense and security structure, which has affected Turkey's new structure in its place and role in European security structure. To reduce concerns arising from the ESDP, Turkey has demanded equal participation in decision-making processes. However, this request was not sympathetic to Turkey's EU. In response, Turkey has used its veto power in NATO and vetoed the NATO cooperation until 2002. As stated earlier, during the Helsinki summit, the EU understood that the CSDP would not be capable and reliable without cooperation with NATO (Aybet and Muftuler-Bac 2000). Due to the continued lack of confidence in Turkey, 'Berlin plus' has continued to veto the implementation of the agreement. ESDP process started after the Helsinki Summit in 1999 led to major problems, especially between the EU and Turkey.

In this case, since the second half of 2001, between England and the United States and Turkey has caused intense negotiations. There were several reasons for Turkey to take part in such an initiative: First of all, Ankara did not want to stay completely out of the process. At the same time, he wanted to get rid of the image of being a country that causes problems for ESDP. The USA, on the other hand, has begun to behave softer against the European Union on ESDP than before. The USA clearly expressed its willingness to leave the task of ensuring security and stability in the Balkans to the EU. In addition, the September 11 attack was effective. Ankara in December 2001 Memorandum of Understanding between the US-UK and Turkey helped to

overcome some of Turkey's security concerns. At the end of talks held between Turkey and the EU, it took the ESDP-NATO cooperation by providing certain guarantees to safeguard Turkey (Howorth, 2007). However, Turkey's difficult to say that he was completely satisfied with this compromise. According to the Memorandum of Ankara, Turkey gave up its claim to defend since 1999. It gave up its demand to join in the decision-making mechanism of operations to be carried out by the EU within the framework of ESDP, independent of NATO. Global terrorism, security risks, threats, etc. has become increasingly common threats in Europe and Turkey. This changing threat perception of both sides has brought changes in their policies towards each other (Oğuzlu, 2003). EU in two thousand and two 2002, giving it a date for starting negotiations and has developed good relations with Turkey for full membership negotiations in 2005.

During this period (2000-2007) Turkey, hoping to become a full member of the EU economy, tried to adapt to the EU *acquis* in the field of politics and law. However, the EU's growing negativity in politics and rhetoric towards Turkey, has shaken the confidence of Turkey's EU. As stated by former enlargement commissioner Rehn also in Europe, Turkey is an anchor of stability in the most unstable parts of the world and is a measure of democracy to the Muslim world. Geostrategic location, historical and religious connections, secular structure, with military capability and experience in Islam and military operations, Turkey could contribute to the EU's security (Abellan, 2008; Muftüler-Bac, 2000). Leaving Turkey outside the security apparatus, the EU does not serve security. This is why there is a need for cooperation between the EU and Turkey with a discourse based on the policy to be developed. Also, for the CSDP and hence the reliability and capacity of the European security and defense, Turkey's EU accession is important. Development of policy based on cooperation between the EU and Turkey, gives a positive message to the Islamic world. It can revise the EU's image and role in the region (Oğuzlu, 2003: 295; Müftüler-Bac, 2000).

EU cooperation with Turkey, would undermine the EU is a Christian club perception. Turkey, the Middle East, the Mediterranean, the Balkans and has close historical and religious ties and relations with the Caucasus, democratic, and secular political structure continues to be the only country to be a model to the Islamic world. In addition, the current strength of the Turkish army, including air, large and naval forces, and the ongoing conflicts around the EU made the Turkish army even more important for the security of Europe and its surroundings. In particular, Turkey's Ankara Agreement in 2002 with NATO, EU and UN multinational participating in the operation conducted by worldwide gained experience in crisis management and humanitarian operations (Bilgin, 2003: 345). As a member of NATO, good intentions handling capabilities in the region, Turkey's conflicted, in CDSP the capacity and credibility of the international peacekeeping will enhance the role of the EU.

Turkey's contribution to the implementation of the CSDP missions since 2002, constitute a good combination for Turkey's EU security and defense policy partnership. It clearly shows that it increases the quality and efficiency in this regard. Turkey's geopolitical position, her energy resources such as oil and natural gas and the Middle East, makes such a center for energy routes between the Caspian region and Europe. Turkey, Middle East, Persian Gulf and the Caucasus to Europe trade has an important role in road transport and energy links. On the other hand, Turkey can act as a buffer in the region and the EU to secure energy routes. Finally, Turkey's stability, security and prosperity There is a close relationship between quality and peace of EU-Turkey relations. cooperative relations on the one hand increases the quality of economic and

democratic development of peace between the EU and Turkey. On the other hand it reduces conflicts and increasing chaos in Turkey. Therefore, cooperation on EU-Turkey relations and security, the EU-Turkey won intraregional importance.

Result

This study examined the relationship between Turkey's EU security and defense architecture. When Europeanization and EU-Turkey relations are examined in study, first said that the security interests of the main motivations behind the European integration and the CSDP. Since the establishment of the EU, Turkey and the EU have been in security cooperation in the Euro-Atlantic security architecture. European security is now under a more complex, multidimensional and fluid threat than Europe has ever encountered. Increasing global terrorism, illegal immigration, risks to energy security pose the main threats to European stability and security. Therefore, the stability and security of Europe has become tightly linked with the stability and security of the Middle East, the Mediterranean and the Caucasus.

Military capability and experience in military operations, geostrategic position, the links with European unstable environment, Turkey can improve the reliability and capacity of the CSDP. The development of cooperative relations between the EU and Turkey, therefore, is very important for the future of European security. The EU's political and Turkey to cooperate on economic and security issues, will contribute to prosperity, safety, the stability of the European Union and the EU'S environment. Accordingly, the CSDP is even more important for Turkey's EU integration. The decisions taken in the Ankara document and at the 2002 Copenhagen Summit are crucial for improving the reliability and capacity of CSDP and NATO cooperation. As seen in the Ankara Agreement process, the continuation of cooperation in the area of Turkey's security is in the interest of all parties on the side (Açıkmeşe ve Dizdaroğlu, 2014:161-162). As a NATO member, Turkey does not want to stay out of the EU security and defense policy. At the same time, Turkey's geostrategic position and with the EU's military capacity had scarcely also be able to resolve some security concerns. From Cold War to today Turkey is more connected with the security bond to European institutions. In the context of ESDI, it wants to join the European army, which is in the formation stage, and to have a say in this formation. Due to security reasons and because of its geostrategic position, Turkey has wanted to take part in the security structure of the EU is trying to create. Also In terms of the EU, it can be said European security will remain incomplete without Turkey.

References

- Abellan, M. M. (2008). Competing Vision of European Foreign and Security Policy Making. Turkey, the European Union and NATO, Garnet Conference, the European Union and international Affairs, Brussels,24-26 April 2008.
- Açıkmeşe, S. A and Cihan Dizdaroğlu, C. (2014). NATO-AB İlişkilerinde İşbirliği ve Çatışma Dinamikleri. *Uluslararası İlişkiler*. 10 (40). 131-163.
- Aybet, G., Muftuler-Bac (2000). Transformation in Security and Identity After the Cold War: Turkey's Problematic Relations with Europe, *International Journal*, Autumn 2000, pp.567-582.
- Bilgin, P. (2003). The "Peculiarity" of Turkey's Position on EU-NATO Military/Security Cooperation: A Rejoinder to Missiroli. *Security Dialogue*, 34(3), 345–349.

Duke, S. (2018). The Enigmatic Role of Defence in the EU: From EDC to EDU?, *Foreign Affairs Review*, 1, p. 63–80.

Howorth, J. (2007). *Security and Defence Policy in the European Union*, Palgrave Macmillan, Houndmills.

Mason, R. (2018). 'The Syria Conflict and the Euro-Med Refugee Crisis: An Opportunity to Enhance the Common Foreign and Security Policy?', *European Foreign Affairs Review*, 1, p. 81–95

Muftuler-Bac, M. (2000). Turkey's role in the EU's Security and Foreign Policies, *Security Dialogue*, 31 (4).

Oğuzlu, H. T. (2003) An Analysis of Turkey's Prospective Membership in the European Union from a Security Perspective, *Security Dialogue* 34(3), pp. 285-299

Öniş, Z. (2001). An Awkward Partnership: Turkey's Relations With The European Union in Comparative-Historical Perspective, Retrieved from <http://home.ku.edu.tr/~zonis/partnership.PDF>.